

Construction of Global Ball for Point Location for Teaching and Learning of Mathematics in Secondary Schools and Colleges

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Abstract

Mathematics is applied in every fields of study and has continued to play a significant role in the growth and development of any country. To achieve the modern day technology in teaching and learning, Mathematics by the year 2025, emphasis should be laid on the use of instructional materials. Instructional materials help to make teaching effective and learning permanent to learners. The purpose of this paper is to construct global ball for point location for teaching and learning of mathematics in secondary schools and colleges. This serves as instructional material and global ball for point location is used for teaching longitude and latitude in senior secondary schools. This paper introduced global ball for point location as an aspect of mathematics and its importance to other aspect of mathematics was discussed. The statement of has reported poor achievement of students in mathematics. Global ball for point location is being introduced to help in the improvement of the standard of mathematics understanding in longitude and latitude. The method of using global ball for point location was introduced. The global ball was made up iron rod and calibrated numbers in degree north and south of the equator and degree west and east of the equator. The use of global ball for point location will enhance effective teaching and learning of mathematics, which will go a long way in encouraging students that are not interested in learning mathematics to develop an in interest, In conclusion, it was recommended that Government should encourage the use of global ball for point location in the teaching and learning of mathematics in all secondary schools. Also, Mathematics teachers should be trained and retrained in the use of global ball for point location to teach different concepts in mathematics. This should be done through seminars, workshops and conferences.

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1.1 Introduction

Mathematics is one of the universal science subjects that occupy an important place in the Nigerian educational system and globally. Hence, it is compulsory for all students in the pre-tertiary education level. But, it is disheartening to know that Nigerian students' academic performance in mathematics over the years has been rated by stakeholders in mathematics education as very poor, except for some outstanding students. The big question now is; what caused students to perform so poorly in mathematics? There are several factors adduced to be responsible for the poor performance of students in mathematics in Delta state over the years. One of the prominent factors is the ineffective use of instructional materials. Instructional materials are essential and significant tools needed for teaching and learning of school subjects to promote teachers' efficacy and improve students' performance. They make learning more interesting, practicable, realistic and appealing. They also enable both the teachers and students to participate actively and effectively in lesson sessions. They give room for acquisition of skilled knowledge and development of self-confidence and self-actualization in educational pursuit. Ibeneme (2020) defined teaching aids as those materials used for practical demonstration in the classroom situation by students and teachers. Ikerionwu (2020) saw instructional materials as objects or devices that assist the teacher to present a lesson to the learners in a logical manner. In his own perspective, Fadeiye (2015) saw instructional materials as visual and audio-visual aids, concrete or non-concrete, used by teachers to improve the quality of teaching and learning activities. Agina-Obu (2015) submitted that instructional materials of all kinds appeal to the sense organs during teaching and learning.

Moreover, Isola (2021) described instructional materials as objects or devices that assist the teachers to present their lessons logically and sequentially to the learners. Oluwagbohunmi and Abdu- Raheem (2014) acknowledged that instructional materials are such used by teachers to aid explanations and make learning of subject matter understandable to students during teaching-learning process. Abdu-Raheem (2014) asserted that non availability and inadequate provision of instructional materials are the major causes of teaching ineffectiveness in schools. Ahmed (2023) had earlier asserted that in most secondary schools in Nigeria, teaching and learning take place under a most un-conducive environment without access to essential learning materials. In 2015, Eniayewu posited that it is very important to use instructional aids for effective teaching and instructional delivery to make students understand concepts and acquire more knowledge for promotion of academic standards in science related subjects in schools. Besides, Ajayi and Ayodele (2019) had earlier stressed on the importance of availability of instructional materials to achieving effectiveness in educational delivery and supervision in the school system. Enaigbe (2019) as well noted that basic materials and textbooks, chalkboard and essential equipment like computers, projectors, television, etc. are not readily available in many schools. The findings of Olumorin, Yusuf, Ajidagba, and Jekayinla, (2018) observed that instructional materials help teachers to teach conveniently and the learners to learn more easily without any problem of understanding. They asserted that instructional materials would have direct contact with all the

sense organs if used. Kochhar (2021) supported that instructional materials are very significant learning and teaching tools. He suggested the need for teachers to find necessary materials for Instruction to supplement what textbooks provide in order to broaden concepts and arouse students' interests in the subject. According to Abolade (2019), the advantages of instructional materials are that they are cheaper to produce, useful in teaching large number of students at a time, encourage learners to pay proper attention and enhance their interest.

However, Akinleye (2021) attested that effective teaching and learning requires a teacher to teach the students with instructional materials and use practical activities to make learning more vivid, logical, realistic and pragmatic. Esu, Enufoha, and Umoren, (2014) agreed that instructional materials are indispensable tools for effective teaching and learning activities. Ekpo (2014) also supported that teaching aids are always used in supporting the sense organs. Despite the fact that instructional materials are essential tools that can make teaching more practicable and knowledge acquisition much easier than anticipated, they are not readily available in Nigerian secondary schools. This leads to low level of performance by students in external examinations (Abdu-Raheem 2014). According to Joshua in Abiodun-Oyebanji and Adu (2017), instructional materials are all the things that are used in teaching/learning process to support, facilitate, influence and encourage acquisition of knowledge, competency and skills. Abdu-Raheem (2014) encouraged teachers to always provide teaching aids during their teaching, because they would enhance learners' full participation in the lesson, provide room for enquiry based learning, problem solving, discussion and clarification of issues and ideas among students and the teacher. Afolabi and Adeleke (2018) identified non-availability, inadequate and non-utilization of learning materials to teach as a result of teachers' poor skilled knowledge which is also responsible for the use of lecture method in teaching mathematics. They recommended that both students, teachers, parents, parents/teachers association, government and philanthropists should pay more emphasis to the provision of instructional materials for the teaching and learning of mathematics in schools. Much earlier, Ogbondah (2018) advocated for teachers' resourcefulness and also encouraged them to always search for necessary instructional materials to complement their teaching of mathematics.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

One cannot avoid considering the utilitarian aspect of mathematics in preparing a pupil for a useful living (Odili, 2016). However, mathematics has been dreaded by many students as a result of impression created in their minds that the subject is difficult. The situation has been further compounded by the quality of instruction offered by mathematics teachers. The trend of students' achievement, according to WAEC report of 2018 reviews abysmal achievement. This has greatly affected enrolment into the science related course in tertiary institutions in Nigeria and Unified Tertiary Matriculations Examination Board (UTME) (2019). Furthermore, Amoo (2020) and Adebajo (2021) also observed that in evidence from research findings shows that student's achievement in Mathematics especially in Algebra. However, in teaching and learning, instructional materials play a key role towards concretizing learning. Instructional materials make learning meaningful and help to improve students' academic achievement. However, these

advantages of instructional materials have not reflected in the education system because of the death of these instructional materials in our school. Hence, the need for alternative instructional materials called improvisation.

Moreover, mathematics is resources intensive and in an era of poor funding or scarcity of resources. It may be very difficult to fund some of the original materials and equipment for the teaching of mathematics in schools adequately, improvisation becomes the next option. Studies have shown the importance of improvisation in teaching of mathematics.

Also, the impact of instructional materials inform of global ball has continued to improve the standard of mathematics understanding of students in developed countries such as the United States and Europe, Odih (2019). Incidentally, in Delta state of Nigeria especially, little or nothing has been done to fully integrate the use of instructional inform of global ball to teach mathematics. The present study therefore sought to construct global ball for point location in finding distant and direction of a place in mathematics instruction.

1.3 Goals and Objectives

The purpose of this project is to construct global ball for teaching colleges and secondary school students on how to find.

- i. The angular distance between two places
- ii. The difference between the latitude and longitude between two places
- iii. To find distance along great circles. (i.e along any of the longitude and distance along the equator or latitude and the equator).
- iv. The bearing and direction of different places.

2.0 Review of Literature

Not much attempt has been geared toward exploring Mathematical global ball in complementing Mathematics instruction. This gap is even amplified by the lack of attention paid to Mathematical global ball by most secondary Mathematical text materials in Nigeria. Even, there are doubts as to whether many of the secondary teacher education programmes in Mathematics pay enough attention to enabling prospective teachers of the subjects acquire necessary competencies in designing and using Mathematical global balls. Games in general serve the purpose of recreation and often generate excitement and spirit of competition, Games serve as reinforcement to both winners (to strive to maintain their lead) and loser (to strive to overcome their defeat). Attempt has been made to categorize instructional activities into developmental and practical activities. Some activities especially introductory ones are to help pupils to understand a concept, these are developmental activities. Other activities are designed, to help pupils to remember a concept or skill; these are practical activities. Instructional materials should be available for development and practice. Presumably, changing methods instructional patterns and use of class time imply changes in utilization of classroom. Under Hill (2017) asserts that research has supported the use of 50 to 75 percent of class time for developmental activities and 25 to 50 percent for practice. However, practice is often a boring experience. Since games release tension, clear boredom and foster an environment where the learner can grow in his or her skills and acquire further knowledge. The planning of appropriate games for learning Mathematics actually depends on both the learners and teachers' ingenuity. Mathematics games though useful, can be abused in the classroom. Especially with the younger students, disorder can be created in the class when the teacher uses the game inappropriately. Here are some guides to the proper utilization of global ball for teaching Latitude and Longitude in the classroom:

1. Use a large wall map or overhead map
2. Create a latitude /longitude chart on the board
3. Handout blank charts like the one on the board for students to complete with you.
4. Select three cities to demonstrate.
5. For latitude: find the equator. Determine if the city is north or south of the equator. Make N or S in the chart on the board.
6. Determine which two lines of latitude the city is in between.
7. Show how to determine the midpoint by splitting the difference between the two lines from step seven.
8. Determine if the city is closer to the midpoint or one of the lines.
9. Estimate the latitude degree and write the answer in the chart on the board.
10. For longitude: find the prime meridian. Determine if the city is east or west of prime meridian. Make E or W in the chart on the board.
11. Determine which two lines of longitude the city is in between.
12. Determine the midpoint by splitting the difference between the two lines.
13. Determine if the city is closer to the midpoint or one of the lines.

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14. Estimate the longitude degree and write the answer in the chart on the board.
15. Use the global ball at the appropriate time. The teacher must decide when to introduce the global ball so as to achieve its result in relation to the concept being taught and objectives. For instance, does the teacher want to facilitate set induction, reinforce an old idea, and remedy the observed deficiencies;
16. Arrange the global ball for point location to allow full participation by all members of your class in everyday play;
17. Plan and organize the global ball for point location carefully so that the informality and excitement of the setting do not defeat its purposes;
18. Emphasize that latitude always measures north and south and longitude always measures east and west.
19. Stress that when doing the measuring students should be hopping from one line to line, not dragging their fingers along one line. Otherwise they would be measuring wrong direction

3.0 Methodology

The design and the development of global ball for point location will be done in the following steps:

3.1 How to Develop the Global Ball for Point Locations

The global ball can be made manual or by using electric gadget. The global ball for point location is made up of metal fixture, 10mm iron rod, 3 inches pipe for pole, galvanized round plate base with nuts, flat pan and 3 1/2 rod for north, south, east and west which include calibrated numbers round the global ball object. The skeletal diagram of the global ball is shown below.

3.2 Method of Using the Global Ball for Teaching and Learning

- i. The latitudes are the vertically curved lines within the spherical shape object.
- ii. The longitudes are horizontal curved lines within the spherical shape object.
- iii. The spherical shape object can be rotated while explaining to the students.
- iv. The various locations of any point on the latitudes and longitudes can be located while rolling the spherical shape object.
- v. The difference between two places on the latitudinal or longitudinal lines can be calculated using formulas for calculating the differences.
- vi. To calculate distance between two points P and Q on the longitudes is given by:
$$\text{Distance PQ} = \frac{\theta}{360} \times 2\pi R$$
- vii. To calculate distance between two points P and Q on the latitudes is given by:

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$$\text{Distance PQ} = \frac{\theta}{360} \times 2\pi R \cos \alpha$$

Conclusion

This paper introduces the practical way of teaching latitudes and longitudes in such a way that when the students are rotating the spherical object they will at the same time be able to learn how to calculate the difference between two points on the global ball. The students are involved mainly in the teaching/learning situation and the rotating the spherical object is more effective and makes it a better and fast understanding of the concept being introduced (that is calculate the difference between two points on the global)

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made due to the result of the study:

1. The government should encourage the use of global ball in the teaching and learning of mathematics in all secondary schools. This will enhance teaching and learning of mathematics
2. The use of global ball in schools will motivate students who lack interest in mathematics to have interest in learning.
3. Mathematics teachers should be trained and retrained on the use of global ball to teach different concept in mathematics. This should be done through seminal, workshop and conferences.
4. Curriculum planners should inculcate global ball method into the curriculum of the students and ensure that it is being implemented for effective teaching and learning of mathematics.

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